

Guiding Questions Values Assessment_3.6

Your assignment consists of developing a concise (1000 - 1,500 words) review of practices and approaches for valuing nature that have been studied, documented, or experienced among the IPLC that you work with. The review would focus on valuation practices that IPLC conduct in their own communities for their own purposes rather than those conducted by outsiders (usually about what communities' value, how and why). The latter type of valuation is being carried out through a systematic review of the literature.

In case you are unfamiliar with the concept of nature valuation, we provide a brief description: Valuation is the process of assigning worth to something - anything. In the case of the IPBES Values Assessment, we are interested in documenting and assessing the different ways that individuals, communities, societies and governments assign worth to nature and its numerous components. In economics, the worth of nature is often expressed in monetary terms, but not only. It's also expressed in terms of time (we - supposedly - spend more time on the things we value more), or in terms of the wellbeing it provides us (we - supposedly - spend time and money on things that make us feel good). Biologists and ecologists value nature in terms of its diversity, its integrity, using indicators such as species richness, amount of biomass, extent of forest cover, quality of water, etc. There are a multitude of methods that are used to determine what is valued. The authors in our chapter of the Values Assessment believe that IPLC also have valuation systems, approaches and methods. They probably vary widely among different groups and regions and across livelihood types.

With the collection of reviews that we will be receiving from other CAs like yourself, we aim to synthesise the contribution and bring to light the multitude of ways that IPLC demonstrate the importance of their relations to nature and how they use these 'valuation processes' for fulfilling different societal objectives.

To assist you with the process and to standardize among the reviews that we will be receiving, we have a series of guiding questions. *We understand that these are a lot of questions, so please don't feel obliged to respond to all of them.* Respond to the ones that you feel most comfortable with and for which you know you have substantial content for.

The guiding questions/instructions are as follows:

1. Please provide a brief background information about the IP or LCs whose valuation approaches you will be describing. For example, geographical location, main source(s) of livelihood (e.g., farmers, agroforestry, hunter-gatherers, herders or pastoralists, fisheries, others)?
2. Please tell us if the review that you have developed resonates with a broader group or category of livelihood or Indigenous peoples, such as Pastoralist communities in Central Asia or Forest communities in Central Africa or Fishery Communities in Northern Europe? Brief description of the socio-political context of the IPLC you will be describing. To what extent do they exercise autonomy? Is the right to self-determination recognized

internationally in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples 2007 effectively enforced in their territories?

3. Please provide a description of how valuation of nature is conducted among the IPLC that you are most familiar with? For example:

- What are the methods and approaches for deciding about preserving nature (Mother Earth)?
- How is nature appreciated, honoured and revered? How is its importance expressed (directly and indirectly)?
- How is valuation of nature or components of nature undertaken? What information, knowledge or understanding is obtained from the process? Who tends to conduct the valuation exercises?
- How does that information feed back into decision making or other type of response?
- How do individuals or groups or key persons manifest the importance of nature? When are such expressions conducted?
- Why are valuations conducted? What purpose do they have? What types of values are elicited or recognized by the process(es)?
- How generalizable are the practices and approaches you are describing to other groups in the broader region?

4. Please describe how the information generated from valuation processes is shared and stored within and beyond the community: What constitutes 'evidence' of the valuation process? What are the standards for evidence among the IPLC?

5. Finally, the References: Please list all sources of 'evidence' that you have consulted to develop this review and cite them accordingly in your text. You can provide links to webpages or documentaries or artwork as well as academic literature in whatever language they are available in. You can also provide any other information material such as images, videos, recordings, paintings, songs, etc. As long as these materials are available publicly and their distribution is approved by the IPLC involved, they will be considered as sources of evidence.